

HUMAN RIGHT'S EDUCATION IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

The right to education is recognised, promoted and protected at all levels from national, regional to international. Education is the primary vehicle by which economically and socially marginalised adults and children can lift themselves out of poverty and obtain the means to participate fully in their communities. Education has a vital role in empowering women, safeguarding children from exploitative and hazardous labor and sexual exploitation, promoting human rights and democracy, protecting the environment, and controlling population growth. Several international conventions, numerous writings and reports by United Nations (UN) bodies stress the importance of the fundamental right to education. The right to education is a fundamental human right. It is also central to realizing other human rights. Education is an extraordinary tool of empowerment. It is essential for the promotion and protection of all human rights. However, too often at both the national and international levels not enough is done to ensure the effective implementation of the right to education. Achieving the right to basic education, as a fundamental human right, is one of the biggest development challenges faced by the international community today. Millions of children, youth and adults remain deprived of basic education.

Key Words: Human Right, Education, India

INTRODUCTION

At international level the ICESCR devotes two articles to the right to education, namely, Articles 13 and 14. Article 13 contains the longest provision in the ICESCR, and is the most wide-ranging and comprehensive article on the right to education in international human rights law. According to Article 13(1) of the ICESCR, states parties agree that all education, whether public or private, formal or non-formal, shall be directed towards the aims and objectives identified in Article 13(1). Interpreted in the light of the World Declaration on Education for All, the Convention on the Rights of the Child, the Vienna Declaration and Programme of Action, and the Plan of Action for the United Nations Decade for Human Rights Education. While all these texts closely correspond to Article 13(1) of the ICESCR, they also include elements, which are not expressly provided for in Article 13(1), such as specific references to gender equality and respect for the environment. These new elements are implicit in and reflect a contemporary interpretation of Article 13(1).

OBJECTIVE

The fundamental obligation in the ICESCR is for the states parties to “take steps” towards realizing the rights enumerated in the ICESCR. This obligation allows a great deal of scope for states to determine the measures they adopt in order to implement the ICESCR. Article 2(2) places special importance on legislative measures, but it clearly also envisages other measures which might include judicial, administrative, financial, educational and social

implementation. Consequently, a lack of legislative measures does not necessarily entail a failure to implement the obligations imposed by the ICESCR because alternative measures may suffice and, indeed, in some circumstances, may be more appropriate. Nevertheless, some legislative measures will usually be necessary. Furthermore, legislative means may be desirable because their public nature leaves them open to effective scrutiny.

RESEARCH MYTHOLOGY

According to Article 13(2)(a) of the ICESCR, primary education shall be compulsory and free to all. Primary education includes the elements of availability, accessibility, acceptability and adaptability, which are common to education in all its forms and at all levels. The Committee took guidance on the proper interpretation of the term “primary education” from the World Declaration on Education for All which states: “[T]he main delivery system for the basic education of children outside the family is primary schooling.” Primary education must be universal, ensure that the basic learning needs of all children are satisfied, and take into account the culture, needs and opportunities of the community. The Declaration further defines “basic learning needs” as “essential learning tools, such as literacy, oral expression, numeracy, and problem solving and the basic learning content such as knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes required by human beings to be able to survive, to develop their full capacities, to live and work in dignity, to participate fully in development, to improve the quality of their lives, to make informed decisions, and to continue learning”. While primary education is not synonymous with basic education, there is a close correspondence between the two. As formulated in Article 13(2)(a), primary education has two distinctive features: it is “compulsory” and “available free to all”. The element of compulsion serves to highlight the fact that neither parents, nor guardians, nor the state are entitled to treat as optional the decision as to whether the child should have access to primary education. The nature of this requirement is unequivocal. The right is expressly formulated so as to ensure the availability of primary education without charge to the child, parents or guardians. Fees imposed by the government, the local authorities or the school, and other direct costs, constitute disincentives to the enjoyment of the right and may jeopardize its realization.

THE RIGHT TO SECONDARY EDUCATION

Article 13(2)(b) applies to secondary education “in its different forms”, thereby recognizing that secondary education demands flexible curricula and varied delivery systems to respond to the needs of students in different social and cultural settings. According to Article 13(2)(b), secondary education “shall be made generally available and accessible to all by every appropriate means, and in particular by the progressive introduction of free education”. The phrase “generally available” signifies, firstly, that secondary education is not dependent on a student’s apparent capacity or ability and, secondly, that secondary education will be transmitted throughout the state in such a way that it is available on the same basis to all. Progressive introduction of free education means that while states must priorities the provision of free primary education, they also have an obligation to take concrete steps towards achieving free secondary and higher education.

Technical and Vocational Education

Technical and vocational education (TVE) forms part of both the right to education and the right to work under Article 6(2) of the ICESCR. Article 13(2)(b) presents TVE as part of secondary education, reflecting the particular importance of TVE at this level of education. However, Article 6(2) does not refer to TVE in relation to a specific level of education; it comprehends that TVE has a wider role, helping “to achieve steady economic, social and cultural development and full and productive employment”. Also, according to Article (1) of the UDHR “technical and professional education shall be made generally available”. Accordingly, the Committee takes the view that TVE forms an integral element of all levels of education.

The Right to Higher Education

Article 13(2)(c) is formulated on the same lines as Article 13(2)(b). There are three differences between the two provisions. Article 13(2)(c) does not include a reference to either education “in its different forms” or specifically to TVE. The third and most significant difference between Article 13(2)(b) and (c) is that while secondary education “shall be made generally available and accessible to all”, higher education “shall be made equally accessible to all, on the basis of capacity”. These two omissions reflect only a difference of emphasis between Article 13(2)(b) and (c). If higher education is to respond to the needs of students in different social and cultural settings, it must have flexible curricula and varied delivery systems, such as distance learning; in practice, therefore, both secondary and higher education have to be available “in different forms. The third and most significant difference between Article 13(2)(b) and (c) is that while secondary education “shall be made generally available and accessible to all”, higher education “shall be made equally accessible to all, on the basis of capacity”.

The Right to Fundamental Education

By virtue of Article 13(2)(d), individuals “who have not received or completed the whole period of their primary education” have a right to fundamental education, or basic education as defined in the World Declaration on Education For All. Since everyone has the right to the satisfaction of their “basic learning needs” as understood by the World Declaration, the right to fundamental education is not confined to those “who have not received or completed the whole period of their primary education”. The right to fundamental education extends to all those who have not yet satisfied their “basic learning needs”. Fundamental education, therefore, is an integral component of adult education and life-long learning. Because fundamental education is a right of all age groups, curricula and delivery systems must be devised which are suitable for students of all ages.

Principle of Compulsory Education Free of Charge for All

Article 14 of the ICESCR requires that each state party which has not been able to secure compulsory primary education free of charge should adopt within two years a detailed plan of action for the progressive implementation of such. In spite of this obligation a number of states parties have neither drafted nor implemented a plan of action for free and compulsory primary education. This obligation is a continuing one and states parties to which the provision is relevant by virtue of the prevailing situation are not absolved from the obligation as a result of their past failure to act within the two-year limit. The plan must cover all of the actions which are necessary in order to secure each of the requisite component parts of the right, and must be sufficiently detailed so as to ensure the comprehensive realization of the right. The right to education, recognized in Articles 13 and 14 of the ICESCR, as well as in a variety of other international treaties, such as the Convention on the Rights of the Child and the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women, Plans of action prepared by states parties to the ICESCR in accordance with Article 14 are especially important as the work of the Committee has shown that the lack of educational opportunities for children often reinforces their subjection to various other human rights violations. For instance, these children, who may live in abject poverty and not lead healthy lives, are particularly vulnerable to forced labor and other forms of exploitation. Is of vital importance.

Right to Education Jurisprudence in India

In India the judiciary has shown its deep concern for providing free and compulsory education to all children below the age of 14 years. The right to free primary education has now been declared as a fundamental right by the Indian Supreme Court. The theory of the complementary nature of rights declared in Part III and Part IV and the harmonious interpretation of these rights has been the foundation for the realization of primary education being declared a fundamental right today in India. The Supreme Court of India in the Bandhua Mukti Morcha. The issue of the scope and extent of right to education came up before the Supreme Court in Mohini Jain case held that the right to education is implicit in and flows from the right to life guaranteed by Article 21. That the right to

education has been treated as one of transcendental importance in the life of an individual has been recognized not only in this country since thousands of years, but all over the world.

Education Policy in India

With a view to realizing the constitutional goals set for education, the government of India in 1964 appointed the Education Commission (1964–1966). The Commission was entrusted with the task of evolving a national system of education. It recommended a radical transformation in the prevailing education system and highlighted the need for the “common school approach” to promote equity and social justice. The first National Policy on Education (NPE), 1968 recommended free and compulsory elementary education and equalization of educational opportunities especially for girls and children belonging to SCs and STs. Another National Policy on Education (NPE–1986) was adopted and further updated in 1992. The NPE 1986 provides for a comprehensive policy framework for the development of education up to the end of the century and a Plan of Action (POA) 1992, assigning specific responsibilities for organizing, implementing and financing its proposals

Right to Education at Primary Level in India

For the first time in the history of education in India a Department for Primary Education has been opened in the Ministry of Human Resource Development at New Delhi. A new primary education policy has been launched under the scheme of Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) at the district level throughout the country in 2001. The assistance under the programme of SSA was on the basis of an 85 to 15 ratio sharing arrangement between the central government and the state government during the Ninth Plan, and at a 75 to 25 ratio during the Tenth Plan, and at 50 to 50 ratio thereafter. ‘Draft Education Bill Upsets Schools’, Times of India, 17 December 2005. The programme covers the entire country, except the State of Goa. The Ministry has also set up a National Mission for SSA under the chairmanship of the prime minister. The first meeting of the Governing Council of National Mission was held on 21 February 2005. The planned allocations for elementary education have increased steadily but are still not quite adequate to fulfill the constitutional commitments. The period following the adoption of National Policy on Education (NPE) 1986 saw the introduction of a number of centrally sponsored schemes to cater to the specific needs of the elementary education sector.

Right to Education at Higher Level in India

The NPE 1986 underscores adult education for the eradication of illiteracy, particularly in the age group of 15–35. A vast programme of adult and continuing education was implemented through various ways and channels, including the establishment of centers in rural areas for continuing education. A number of programmes taken up to impart adult education during the last four decades before launching of the National Literacy Mission in May 1988 could not be very successful on account of a number of inherent weaknesses such as the low levels of literacy, centre-based approach, lack of mass awareness and community participation. However, the government of India continues to pursue the mass literacy mission, which ultimately brought encouraging results. The number of illiterates during the decade 1991–2001 came down from 329 million in 1991 to 304 million in 2001. This was a welcome change in the depressing scenario. The scheme of continuing education provides a learning continuum to the efforts of Total Literacy and Post-Literacy Programmers’ in the country. The main thrust is on providing further learning opportunities to neo-literates by setting up Continuing Education Centers (CECs) and Nodal Continuing Education Centers (NCECs), to serve a population of about 2000–2500 people by providing facilities of libraries, reading rooms, learning centers, sports and cultural centers and other individual interest promotion programmes’. As a part of this strategy, there is stress on establishing rural libraries, which will provide reading and learning material to neo-literates in their own languages. Wide acceptance of this programme is achieved by involving non-governmental organizations, voluntary agencies, social workers, and Panchayati Raj institutions in the planning and implementation of the scheme of continuing education. Various development departments, technical institutions, professional groups and the Directorate of Adult Education, Government of India provide the input needed by the programme. State Resource Centers (SRCs) and Jan Shikshan Sansthan join hands by giving the necessary resource

and training support. The social mobilization generated by the literacy campaigns has had an enormous impact on other social sectors, most notably women's empowerment, health and population stabilization along with environmental awareness. A framework for effective social action has been provided by the Panchayati Raj Institutions. The campaigns have served the cause of promoting equity and social justice in society and fostering of a scientific temper and a sense of belonging to India's great composite culture and consciousness of unity in diversity.

CONCLUSION

The ICESCR provides for progressive realization and acknowledges the constraints due to the limits of available resources. It also imposes on states parties various obligations which are of immediate effect. States have a specific and continuing obligation "to move as expeditiously and effectively as possible" towards the full realization of Article 13. States parties must closely monitor education including all relevant policies, institutions, programmers', spending patterns and other practices so as to identify and take measures to redress any de facto discrimination. Education operates as a multiplier, enhancing the enjoyment of all individual rights and freedoms where the right to education is effectively guaranteed, while depriving people of the enjoyment of many rights and freedoms where the right to education is denied or violated.

In the last 60 years the government of India has evolved very successful programmers' in imparting primary education in the country. Primary education is now provided in the mother tongue or regional language in all the states and union territories (UTs). There has been substantial increase in access to elementary education, with reduced class, caste and sectional disparities. Despite substantial achievements, the task of universal elementary education (UEE) is far from complete. Enrolments in the schools have certainly increased but so have the number of out of school children. Sadly, the country today has one of the largest illiterate populations in the world. Caste, gender, class and regional disparities in UEE though reduced are still glaring and persistent. The educational administration in most states and UTs has yet to effectively tackle endemic problems concerning shortage of teachers, teacher absenteeism, inadequate and improperly designed school buildings, lack of teaching/learning equipment, need-based teacher training, and a curriculum related to real life requirements.

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